

Effect of low energy oxygen ion beam irradiation on Structural and Electrical properties of PEDOT: PSS Thin films and PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ Nanocomposites

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Abstract - Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): Poly (styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS), is one of the promising conducting polymers. Its conductivity is generally around 1 S/cm, which severely limits its use in many of the applications. An ion irradiation plays an important role to modify the properties of the polymers. When ion beam irradiates the PEDOT: PSS film, the bond breaking, re-arrangement of polymer structure modifies the structural and electrical properties of the PEDOT: PSS. In the present study, an attempt is made to enhance the conductivity of PEDOT: PSS thin films and PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ nanocomposites by low energy oxygen ion irradiation. The effect of low energy oxygen ion beam irradiation on structural and electrical properties of PEDOT: PSS thin films and PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ thin films were studied by FTIR, XRD, SEM and conductivity using Vander pau method. The conductivity of PEDOT: PSS thin films increases for low fluency ion beam irradiation on PEDOT: PSS thin films and decreases for higher fluency.

Keywords – Pedot Pss, Conducting polymers, Oxygen ion irradiation, Low-energy ion beam, Structural modification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conducting polymers have attracted considerable interests in the fields of fundamental and applied research, due to their highly conductive, transparent, stability and flexible properties. A number of efforts to develop highly conductive, solution-processable, and inherently conducting polymer materials based on poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly (styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS), which are suitable for use as transparent electrode materials have been reported (1–4). PEDOT: PSS is one of the most widely used materials in organic devices, including small-molecule organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), polymer light-emitting diodes (PLEDs), and organic photovoltaic (OPV) cells (5–8). PEDOT: PSS is also one of the most studied conducting polymers in both the academic and industrial fields because of its advantages such as high ionization potential, high conductivity, high stability in the oxidized state, and its ability to incorporate water-soluble

polyelectrolytes. PEDOT: PSS usually acts as an interface layer between the indium tin oxide (ITO) anode and the active organic semiconductor layer to improve carrier transport and modify the morphology of ITO. The properties and formulations of PEDOT: PSS are also highlighted in several relevant transparent circuitry applications such as inorganic electroluminescent devices, flexible touch screens, and liquid crystal displays (9–12). To increase the conductivity of the PEDOT: PSS film, the coating properties (annealing times) are controlled and adjusted by carefully formulating the coating ingredients. This technique has been widely discussed in many reports (13–17). Several researchers also point out that changing the ratio of the conducting PEDOT to the insulating PSS or adding a secondary dopant can effectively enhance the conductivity of DOT: PSS films (18–20).

Ion irradiation plays an important role to modify the properties of Polymers. The interaction of ions with polymers lead to the chain scission (bond breaking) formation of free radicals, cross-linking, degradation

etc. Breaking of bonds and re-arrangement of polymer structure modifies the structural and electrical properties of the polymers.

In this study, we used an effective process of low energy oxygen ion irradiation on thin PEDOT: PSS films and PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ nanocomposite thin films. The increase in the conjugation length of PEDOT polymer chains to cause notable changes in structural and film conductivity for different fluencies of an ion beam irradiation on PEDOT: PSS thin films.

Experimental procedure

Preparation of PEDOT: PSS thin films

PEDOT: PSS aqueous solution with 1.3wt% (Sigma-Aldrich) was used for the thin films preparation. Microscopic glass slides were used as substrate. Initially the glass slides are sonicated at 500C with DI water, Ethanol and acetone in each for 20 min then it was dried in an oven at 100-0C for 2h.

Solution was drop casted on the substrate. The casted substrate was dried in an oven at 1000C for 1 hour in order to remove the solvent in the thin film. The thin films were prepared in seven sets. Six of seven samples were irradiated with low energy oxygen ion beam in Inter University Acceleration centre (IUAC) New Delhi. The samples were irradiated with oxygen ion beam (Energy 100keV, Current 500nA) at different fluencies (1x10¹²ions/cm², 1x10¹³ions/cm², 1x10¹⁴ions/cm², 5x10¹²ions/cm², 5x10¹³ions/cm², 5x10¹⁴ions/cm²).

Preparation of PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ nanocomposites thin films

PEDOT: PSS aqueous solution with 1.3 wt% and TiO₂ aqueous solution with 20wt% (Sigma-Aldrich) were mixed at different concentrations using ultra-sonicator. Microscopic glass slides were used as substrates. Initially the glass slides were sonicated at 500c with DI water, Ethanol and acetone in each for 20 min then it was dried in an oven at 1000C for 2h. Solutions of different ratio were drop casted on the substrate. The casted substrate was dried in an oven at 1000C for 1 hour in order to remove the solvent in the thin film. The structural and electrical properties of un-irradiated and irradiated samples were studied using SEM, FTIR and XRD. Conductivity

measurement was carried out for the Un-irradiated and irradiated samples using Four probe technique.

Results and discussions

The morphology of PEDOT: PSS thin films with and without ion irradiation were characterized by SEM technique. Fig. 1 compares the surface morphology of un-irradiated PEDOT: PSS and thin films irradiated at different fluencies. Homogeneous smooth surface was observed in the pure PEDOT: PSS thin film (Fig.1a) When the PEDOT: PSS surface was exposed to ion beam irradiation, the surface roughness increases with increasing fluency (Fig. 1b,1c,1d). PEDOT grains were observed on the film surface, as well as enlarged patterns during the ion beam irradiation. The formation of patterns might be due to micelle formation of the polymeric stabilizer PSS surrounding the nuclei as a result of ion irradiation.

The degradation is due to oxidative process within the PEDOT chains interrupting the free charge carrier through the polymer chain.

Structural characterization by XRD study

The X-ray diffraction pattern of un-irradiated PEDOT: PSS thin film indicates that the polymer is amorphous in nature and shows a broad peak at $2\theta = 18^\circ$ and 26°

The irradiated samples show an identical diffraction pattern except broadening of the peak with increase in fluency. This broadening of peak suggests that polymer is getting into more disorder state.

Structural characterization by FTIR study

Conductivity study of PEDOT: PSS Thin films

Sample Name	Conductivity (S/cm)
Un-irradiated PEDOT:PSS	0.8
Irradiated PEDOT:PSS(5x10E12)	12.4
Irradiated PEDOT:PSS(5x10E13)	37
Irradiated PEDOT:PSS(5x10E14)	18

At relatively low fluencies of ion beam free radical formation takes place via chain scission. Cross-linking occurs when free radicals recombine, essentially reforming the electrical pathway through the samples and increasing the conductivity of the samples.

Effect of ion beam irradiation on Structural and Electrical properties of PEDOT: PSS/TiO2 Nanocomposite Thin films.

The structural and Electrical characterization were done by SEM, XRD, FTIR and four probe technique.

Sample Name	Conductivity (S/cm)
Un-irradiated PEDOT:PSS/TiO ₂	12
Irradiated PEDOT:PSS/TiO ₂ (5x10 ¹²)	84
Irradiated PEDOT:PSSTiO ₂ (5x10 ¹³)	137
Irradiated PEDOT:PSSTiO ₂ (5x10 ¹⁴)	96

Fig.1. Comparison of the surface morphology of non-irradiated and ion irradiated PEDOT: PSS/TiO2 thin films at different fluencies.

XRD Study of PEDOT: PSS/TiO2

II. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of Ion irradiation on structural and Electrical properties of PEDOT: PSS thin film were studied. The conductivity of PEDOT: PSS and PEDOT: PSS/TiO₂ nanocomposite thin films upon ion irradiation increases due the structural changes in PEDOT: PSS. The structural changes may be due to interaction of ions with PEDOT: PSS lead to the chain scission (bond breaking) formation of free radicals, cross-linking, degradation. Breaking of bonds and re-arrangement of polymer of polymer structure modifies the structural and electrical properties of the polymers. The degradation is due to oxidative process within the PEDOT chains interrupting the free charge carrier through the polymer chain.

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